

Examination of Self-Efficacy and Life Satisfaction Levels of Students Receiving Education in Schools of Physical Education and Sports

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Abstract—The purpose of this study is to examine the self-efficacy and life satisfaction levels of students receiving education in schools of physical education and sports. The population of the study consisted 263 students, among which 154 were male and 109 were female (\bar{X} age=19,4905 \pm 2,5605), that received education in the schools of physical education and sports of Selcuk University, Inonu University, Gazi University and Karamanoglu Mehmetbey University. In order to achieve the purpose of the study, the self-efficacy scale, which was developed by Jarrusselam and Shwarzer (1981) [1] and adapted to Turkish by Yesillay (1993) [2], and the life satisfaction scale, developed by Diener, Emmos, Larsen and Griffin (1985) [3] and adapted to Turkish by Kokler (1991) [4], were utilized. For analyzing and interpreting data Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, t-test and one way anova test were used, while for determining the difference between the groups Tukey test and Multiple Linear Regression test were employed and significance was accepted at $P < 0,05$. SPSS (Statistical package for social sciences) package software was used for evaluating the data and finding out the calculated values. In conclusion of this study, it was determined that female students have higher life satisfaction levels than male students, while students attending to the second grade had higher life satisfaction levels than fourth grade students. On the other hand, general self-efficacy levels of male students were found out to be higher than that of female students. It was also determined that students attending to the fourth grade had higher general self-efficacy levels than those receiving education in the first grade. Availability of a significant relation was determined between life satisfaction levels and self-efficacy levels.

Keywords—Physical Education And Sports, Student, Life Satisfaction, Self-Efficacy

I. INTRODUCTION

PERCEIVED self-efficacy is defined as the judgments of people concerning their capacity to perform and organize actions required to attain a predefined performance [5]. Teacher self-efficacy, on the other hand, refers to the beliefs of teachers concerning their capacity to perform and organize an action which is necessary to achieve the duty of teaching in a certain context [6].

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Teacher self-efficacy based on social-cognitive theory is conceptualized as the personal beliefs of teachers concerning the skills of realization, organization and planning of necessary activities to attain given educational objectives [7].

According to Billheimer'e (2006) [8] high teacher self-efficacy affects decision making, enhancing the interest of the family towards school and creating a positive school atmosphere. The higher teacher self-efficacy results in higher probability of overcoming obstacles insistently and resisting failure [9]. Teachers with a strong self-efficacy tend to show specific and observable behaviors such as comfort, struggle, insistence and effort.

These teachers spend more time for the learning of their students and behave in a more responsible and sincere manner particularly for the students with low achievement [10]. Life satisfaction is the combination of the processes of patterns of life and life standards of individuals. Variables such as economic condition, professional status, conditions of the environment they work and expectation levels are the factors affecting life satisfaction of teachers. As a result, the way teachers perceive their job satisfaction and burn out affect their life satisfaction [11].

Professional or working time has a significant role in an individual's life and even if it does not increase the level of attaining individual aims, it increases life satisfaction. Life satisfaction is also defined as the degree of attaining one's predetermined goals [12].

Positive relationship between self-efficacy and life satisfaction can be understood from the fact that individuals with high self-efficacy have the capacity to overcome stressful situations. The individuals with a high self-efficacy have a "can-do" attitude [16].

II. METHOD

A. Research group

The population of the study consisted 263 students, among which 154 were male and 109 were female (\bar{X} age=19,4905 \pm 2,5605), that received education in the schools of physical education and sports of Selcuk University, Inonu University, Gazi University and Karamanoglu Mehmetbey University.

B. Data Collection

In order to achieve the purpose of the study, the self-efficacy scale, which was developed by Jarrusselam and Shwarzer (1981) [1] and adapted to Turkish by Yesillay (1993) [2], and the life satisfaction scale, developed by Diener, Emmos, Larsen and Griffin (1985) [3] and adapted to Turkish by Kokler (1991) [4], were utilized.

C. Analysis of Data

For analyzing and interpreting data Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, t-test and one way anova test were used, while for determining the difference between the groups Tukey test and Multiple Linear Regression test were employed and significance was accepted at $P < 0.05$. SPSS (Statistical package for social sciences) package software was used for evaluating the data and finding out the calculated values.

III. FINDINGS

TABLE I

T TEST RESULTS OF LIFE SATISFACTION LEVELS OF STUDENTS STUDYING IN SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS ACCORDING TO GENDER VARIABLE

	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	p
Male	154	24,6104	5,2919	-2,745	0,006
Female	109	26,3670	4,8451		

As indicated in Table I, there was a significant difference between life satisfaction levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to gender [t value = -2.745 $P = 0.006 < 0.05$]. Mean values showed that life satisfaction level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 24.6104$) while life satisfaction level of female students was ($\bar{X} = 26.3670$).

TABLE II

TEST RESULTS OF SELF-EFFICACY LEVELS OF STUDENTS STUDYING IN SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS ACCORDING TO GENDER VARIABLE

	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	p
Male	154	32,8440	4,5667	-2,556	0,011
Female	109	31,3701	4,6343		

As indicated in Table II, there was a significant difference between self-efficacy levels of the students studying in physical education and sports college according to gender [t value = -2.556 $P = 0.011 < 0.05$]. Mean values showed that self-efficacy level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 32.8440$) while self-efficacy level of female students was ($\bar{X} = 31.3701$).

TABLE III

ONE WAY ANOVA RESULTS OF SELF-EFFICACY LEVELS OF STUDENTS STUDYING IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS COLLEGE ACCORDING TO GENDER VARIABLE

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P	tukey test
Between Groups	170,462	3	56,821	2,663	0,048	4 -1
Within Groups	5506,443	259	21,260			

As indicated in Table III, there was a significant difference between self-efficacy levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [F value = 2.663 $P = 0.048 < 0.05$]. Self-efficacy level of 4.grade students was found to be higher than those of 1.grade students.

TABLE IV

ONE WAY ANOVA RESULTS OF LIFE SATISFACTION LEVELS OF STUDENTS STUDYING IN SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS ACCORDING TO GRADE LEVEL VARIABLE

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P	tukey test
Between Groups	211,578	3	70,526	2,684	,047	2-4
Within Groups	6805,304	259	26,275			

As indicated in Table IV, there was a significant relationship between life satisfaction level of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [F value = 2.684 $P = 0.047 < 0.05$]. It was found that life satisfaction levels of 2.grade students were higher than those of 4.grade students.

TABLE V

CORRELATION ANALYSIS BETWEEN SELF-EFFICACY AND LIFE SATISFACTION LEVELS OF STUDENTS STUDYING IN SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS

	Self-Efficacy	Life Satisfaction
r	1,000	,479
p	,	,000
n	263	263

As indicated in Table V, there was a positive significant relationship between self-efficacy and life satisfaction level of the students studying in physical education and sports college ($r = 0.479$ $p < 0.05$).

IV. DISCUSSION AND RESULT

There was a significant difference between life satisfaction levels of the students who were studying in school of physical education and sports [$P < 0.05$]. Mean values showed that life satisfaction level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 24.6104$) while life satisfaction level of female students was ($\bar{X} = 26.3670$). Based on these results life satisfaction level of female students was found to be higher than that of male students. The findings of the present study are consistent with the findings of Salvadaor et al., (2009) [14], Cromie (2000) [15], Salvador and Mayoral (2011) [16], Lent et al., (2011) [17].

It was found that there was a significant difference between self-efficacy levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports [$P < 0.05$]. Mean values showed that life satisfaction level of male students was ($\bar{X} = 32.8440$) while life satisfaction level of female students was ($\bar{X} = 31.3701$). Based on these results it was observed that male students had higher self-efficacy levels than female students. These results reveal that male students are more active in ensuring teacher self-efficacy based on social-cognitive theory, in performing necessary activities to attain given educational objectives and in developing organizing and planning skills.

The findings of the present study are consistent with the findings of Crick (1998) [18], Scherer et al., (1990) [19], Sanchez et al., (2007) [20], Athayde (1999) [21], Thompson (1999) [22].

It was found that there was a significant difference between self-efficacy levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports according to grade level variable [$P<0.05$]. Self-efficacy levels of 4. grade students were found to be higher than those of 1. grade students. This indicates that 4. grade students have higher achievement experiences and cognitive development levels. The difference between life satisfaction levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports was found to be significant according to grade level variable [$P<0.05$]. It was found that 2. grade students had higher life satisfaction levels than 4. grade students.

These results indicate that individuals and other time periods indicated leisure influenced by levels of emotional response or attitude reveals the outcome. It was found that there was a positive and significant relationship between self-efficacy and life satisfaction levels of the students studying in school of physical education and sports ($p<0.05$). Regarding the feeling of personal achievement as a positive life experience as Bandura suggested, it can be stated that its contribution to general self-efficacy will also be positive. The findings of the present study are consistent with the findings of Dufy and Lent (2009) [23], Judge and Watanabe (1993) [24], Brunstein (1993) [25], Lucas et al., (1996) [26], Wiese and Freud (2005) [27], Maier and Brunstein (2001) [28], Verbruggen and Sels (2010) [29]. In general terms, the present study indicates that individuals having high levels of general self-efficacy are more successful in determining their goals and reaching their goals, and that individuals who achieved their goals can get more satisfaction from life. The more realistically the general self-efficacy is perceived, the individual will be able to determine the goals it wants to achieve that realistically and in this way will minimize its failure possibility. In this connection, the individual will also reduce the possibility of its failure to negatively affect its general self-efficacy level and life satisfaction level. For this reason, the individual's personal awareness and its realistic perception experiences concerning itself have to be increased in both family and school education. By enabling the individual to know itself well, its chance to be successful by determining goals in line with its self-efficacy perception will be increased and this in turn will affect its general self-efficacy and life satisfaction levels positively.

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